

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SEIWOH****FIRST NAME: FATMATA LUCIA****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: SIX****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. **For effective academic writing, the researcher or student must do the following sequentially**

- Discuss with others and put your thoughts and theirs together.
- Gather some ideas from various sources, consult previous authors, and start writing.
- Start with the body and work paragraph by paragraph; write the introduction and conclusion after the body; do not lose track of the question or draft and edit and work out your argument; revise your first draft extensively; make sure the entire essay flows and that the paragraphs are in a logical order; proof-read your final draft carefully; check spelling and punctuation.¹**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Gulma, Kabiru. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1*, Fifth edition. (Washington DC: Euclid University, 2024), 11.

- Scribble all information from various sources, prepare a writing plan, and write the essay till the end before proofreading.

2. **Euclid University recommends these types of English while writing essays:**

- Any English.
- British English ONLY.
- American English ONLY.²**
- British and American English together.

3. **The kind of data sources that would help the researcher to keep up with current research, find out other points of view, and develop models for one's research and analysis are:**

- all three sources of data because they are all equally important.
- Tertiary sources of data.
- Primary sources of data are firsthand.
- Secondary data sources.³**

4. **Research is considered good when it**

- Ask a question worth asking, find an answer that you can support with good reasons, find good data that you can use as reliable evidence to support your**

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 41.

³ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth Edition (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 36.

reasons, draft an argument that makes a good case for your answers, and revise that draft until readers think you met the first four goals.⁴

- Only provides direct information from the researcher.
- Considers generating information from only one source.
- Does not argue different views and opinions but accepts any piece of information.

5. Citation is a must in any good research work because it

- Shows that the researcher knows how to cite information.
- It makes the reading of the research work interesting.
- It is important to give credit to other people's work, re-assures readers about the accuracy of your facts, help readers to follow or extend your research.⁵**
- It adds to the number of words written.

6. The author-date style citation requires

- Notes and bibliography.
- placing a superscript number at the end of the sentence and explain that superscript number as a note providing the author, title, and facts of publication, including relevant page numbers.
- citing it once writing its source in full in the note and citing the exact text subsequently will accommodate the notes.

⁴ Turabian et al., 23.

⁵ Turabian et al., 139–40.

the use of parenthesis instead of superscript numbers; the use of the author, date, and page numbers placed right after the reference in the text, and all sources will be listed in the reference.⁶

7. **An organized dissertation research must entail the following in sequence**

Acronyms, list of tables and figures, abstract, introduction, main content, and conclusion.

Dedication, acknowledgment, Abstract, Chapters 1, 2, to the end.

The Title, the Supervisory Committee Page, Dedication, Acknowledgements, Table of Contents, List of Tables, List of Figures, Biography, Abstract, Chapter 1 – Introduction (Statement of the Problem Research Questions Social Significance), Chapter 2 – Review of the Literature (Critical Analysis of the Literature Research Questions Operational Definition of Terms), Chapter 3 – Method (Methodology), Chapter 4 – Findings Research Questions, Chapter 5 – Discussion Research Question, Limitation of study, Implications, conclusions.⁷

As the researcher wishes.

8. **The review of the literature in dissertation research**

⁶ Turabian et al., 142.

⁷ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 21–23.

- helps the reader understand the variables that will be examined in the dissertation, as well as justifies the research questions being discussed in the dissertation research.**⁸
 - Provides bulk of information for the researcher to meet the number of pages or words to write.
 - It is not geared to provide support to the research questions.
 - Limits the researcher's findings.
9. **What does it mean to organize and plan carefully for dissertation research to be successful?**
- Keep all other issues of life aside and focus on the dissertation.
 - Create and operate a physical, mental, and intellectual workspace, creating a system for organizing and managing your work by developing a writing routine and starting to keep records of information, managing time, saving all drafts, managing thinking, and saving all information.**⁹
 - Read all the time.
 - Read and keep all information in one's head without taking notes.

⁸ Sampson, 38.

⁹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*, Fourth Edition (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications Inc., 2019), 110–32.

10. According to the European Commission, the recommended style of English for the public should be:

- Colloquial British English.
- Combination of American and British English.
- British English is preferred, but very colloquial British usage should be avoided.**¹⁰
- Any English, as long as the message is communicated despite the audience.

¹⁰ European Commission, *English Style Guide - A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, Eighth ed. (European Union, 2021), 7.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Fourth Edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications Inc., 2019.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.